

Axis: Smart Glove Integration for Arabic Sign Language Recognition and Speech Synthesis

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Abstract- This paper introduces an innovative system that enhances communication for Arabic Sign Language (ASL) users by integrating flex sensors, gyroscope, and artificial intelligence in a glove. The embedded sensors enable real-time detection of intricate hand movements during sign language articulation. The system translates user sign language input into text, refines it using the GPT-3 API for grammatical accuracy, and then converts it into clear Arabic speech using Tacotron2. This integrated process ensures a seamless and effective means of expression. Our approach focuses on sensor integration, grammar check, and speech synthesis, providing a comprehensive solution to Arabic Sign Language communication with flexible language options to cater to individual preferences.

Keywords- Arabic Sign Language, Assistive Communication, Gesture Recognition, Sign Language, Speech Synthesis

I. INTRODUCTION

Effective human interaction has historically hinged on robust communication systems within societies. The deaf and hearing-impaired community relies on sign language as a pivotal tool for interpersonal communication. Although sign language facilitates seamless communication within the hearing-impaired community, challenges emerge when attempting to engage with individuals beyond their social circle.

Deaf individuals often encounter significant obstacles when trying to communicate with those outside their immediate community. While sign language serves as an effective means of communication among deaf individuals, it may not be readily understood by individuals who do not share their proficiency in sign language. This communication barrier can lead to feelings of isolation and frustration for deaf individuals as they navigate daily interactions in a predominantly hearing world. Therefore, there is an urgent need to address these challenges and improve accessibility for deaf individuals in various societal contexts. By enhancing effective communication. We can work towards creating a more inclusive and supportive environment for all individuals, regardless of their hearing ability.

Out of the Middle East's 350 million people, over 11 million have disabling hearing loss, comparable to other regions. But services for deaf citizens have not kept pace. The dearth of sign language interpreters is partly a problem of inadequate recruitment and training, and partly a reflection of broader obstacles for deaf citizens. [1]

The lack of focus on Arabic Sign Language has been a significant obstacle for researchers in the field, hindering the progress of developmental efforts within the Arabic context. This provides a huge opportunity for researchers to sign, especially since Arabic is the native language for nearly 300 million people in 20 different countries across the Middle East and North Africa (MENA). [2]

II. RELATED WORKS

In [3], their classification system was built using a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). Where their system classifies images of Arabic Sign Language to text. Then they use Google where the generated Arabic Texts will be converted into Arabic speech. In this stage, Google Text to Speech (GTTS) is used.

In [4], American Sign Language (ASL) is implemented, where the sign detection part is done using a glove with flex and contact sensors to detect finger movements and palm bending. An accelerometer is used to measure the acceleration produced by changing hand positions. The authors do not go into details about the conversion of text to speech. Figure 1 illustrates their proposed approach.

Fig 1: Glove with integrated sensors.

In [5], the glove used in the hand-talking system (HTS) incorporates flex sensors, which are used to detect the bending of each finger. The sensors are connected to a voltage divider arrangement with a 10kohm resistor to measure the bending of each finger accurately. The system is built for English and Arabic sign languages.

In [6], the authors decided to incorporate extra components into the glove. Figure 2 showcases the block diagram of their proposed solution. The glove has an accelerometer and a gyroscope, which help detect hand orientation and enables the recognition of rotated hand signs.

Fig 2: Block Diagram

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

One of the primary challenges arises from the intricacies of the Arabic script itself. Unlike many mainstream languages, Arabic comprises of a larger set of letters, each with multiple forms based on their position in a word. The complexity of Arabic letters, combined with the nuances of Arabic Sign Language, demands a sophisticated recognition system that can accurately distinguish between various gestures.

In the Arabic language, there are different rare sounds of many letters, and due to clusters of consonants, it sounds a bit more complex than other languages. [7]

Another reason Arabic is considered difficult is because of the special characters used in every Arabic word. These special characters are changed relative to the meaning conveyed in the sentence. [7]

Moreover, the sheer number of letters in the Arabic alphabet presents a formidable task. While other sign language recognition systems may focus on languages with fewer symbols, Arabic requires a more extensive mapping and interpretation of gestures. This poses a challenge in terms of both the computational capacity needed for processing a larger dataset and the intricacy of recognizing a more extensive array of distinct signs.

Basic flex sensors, commonly employed in sign language recognition systems, may fall short of capturing the intricacies of Arabic gestures. Arabic Sign Language often involves subtle and nuanced hand movements, requiring a more refined sensor setup. The inclusion of a gyroscope adds complexity but is necessary to capture the dynamic and three-dimensional nature of Arabic Sign Language expressions.

The challenge lies not only in the technical integration of sensors but also in the cultural and linguistic understanding required to interpret the diverse range of gestures inherent in Arabic Sign Language. Overcoming these challenges is crucial for the successful development of a smart glove system that

can accurately and comprehensively recognize Arabic Sign Language gestures.

The Arabic text-to-speech development is quite difficult by itself. Developing an Arabic text-to-speech system presents unique challenges primarily due to the scarcity of publicly available speech corpora in the Arabic language. Unlike English, where large and diverse speech datasets exist, the limited availability of Arabic speech data hampers the training of high-quality speech synthesizers. [12]

This scarcity not only impedes the accessibility of sufficient training material but also restricts the diversity and variability required for robust model training. Additionally, existing Arabic speech synthesis solutions often suffer from slow processing speeds, subpar quality, and a lack of naturalness compared to their English counterparts. [12]

These deficiencies stem from the intricate linguistic characteristics of Arabic, including its complex phonetic and phonological features, as well as the nuances of intonation, stress, and rhythm, which are integral for producing natural-sounding speech. Moreover, the current reliance on relatively small datasets for Arabic speech synthesis underscores the importance of innovative approaches such as transfer learning and neural deep network architectures to overcome these challenges and advance the development of high-quality Arabic speech synthesis systems. [12]

Constructing an Arabic grammar check system presents considerable challenges owing to the intricacies of Arabic grammar and its rich morphological features. These complexities extend to various linguistic levels, including orthography, morphology, syntax, and semantics, introducing inherent ambiguity that complicates the task of error detection and correction. [13]

The scarcity of high-quality parallel data and benchmark datasets specific to Arabic Grammatical Error Correction (GEC) poses significant obstacles in training and evaluating models for this task. The limited availability of resources and the predominant focus of research on GEC in non-English languages, including Arabic, exacerbate the difficulty in accurately detecting and rectifying Arabic grammar errors. As a result, developing an effective Arabic grammar check system necessitates innovative approaches and dedicated efforts to address these linguistic challenges and data limitations. [13]

IV. METHODOLOGY

Our smart glove is carefully crafted, featuring five flex sensors—each aligned with a specific finger—and a gyroscope strategically positioned on the palm's back. These sensors are seamlessly connected to a Raspberry Pi 3, as portrayed in Figure 4. Through the collective insights from these sensors, we engineer a cohesive system geared towards classifying letters based on the amalgamated values of flex sensors and the gyroscope.

This amalgamation of sensor outputs forms the bedrock of our letter classification mechanism. By consolidating these sensory inputs, we establish a comprehensive framework for recognizing and deciphering the nuanced hand movements intrinsic to Arabic Sign Language. This integration not only heightens the system's responsiveness to subtle finger actions but also ensures a holistic portrayal of gestures, contributing to the precision and dependability of our letter classification process.

Fig 3: Arabic Sign Language Letters

In Axis, we meticulously link each Arabic Sign Language letter with a distinct range of flex sensor values for each finger, accompanied by a unique gyroscope axis values. These collective sensor values serve as a comprehensive representation of a specific letter in Arabic Sign Language, as illustrated in Figure 3. To streamline this process, we have established predefined sensor value ranges, meticulously stored in our system.

These ranges were derived through a meticulous recording process, capturing, and saving sensor values associated with each letter for subsequent inference. Table 1 showcases the example range of values for each Arabic letter.

This approach ensures that our system is finely tuned to recognize the nuanced gestures of Arabic Sign Language, offering a robust foundation for accurate letter classification. The pre-established sensor value ranges act as a reference guide during the real-time inference phase, enabling the system to swiftly and precisely interpret user-signed letters based on the stored benchmarks.

In Figure 5 it provides a graphical depiction of the operational flow of Axis, illustrating how the system functions in a step-by-step manner. Initially, the user's input, consisting of a

series of hand signs akin to constructing words in a sentence, is represented visually.

Subsequently, the constructed sentence undergoes two critical steps aimed at enhancing its quality. First, it is subjected to the GPT-3 API, a powerful language model provided by OpenAI, which examines the sentence for any grammatical errors or linguistic inconsistencies present in the user's sign language input. This phase serves to refine and improve the syntactical accuracy and coherence of the sentence, ensuring that it adheres to the grammatical conventions of the Arabic language.

Following the grammar correction process, the refined sentence proceeds to the next stage, where it encounters an Arabic Text-to-Speech. This system is designed to transform the corrected sentence, now linguistically polished and grammatically sound, into clear and natural-sounding Arabic speech. Through this transformation, the user's sign language input is effectively translated into audible speech.

Fig 4: Completed glove with all integrated sensors.

We used a pre-trained Arabic Text-to-Speech model based on Tacotron2 to convert our text to speech adapted from [8]. We utilized HiFi-GAN as our vocoder [8]. HiFi-GAN consists of one generator and two discriminators: multi-scale and multi-period discriminators. The generator and discriminators are trained adversarially, along with two additional losses for improving training stability and model performance. [9]

Table 1. Flex sensor and Gyroscope Axis values

Letters	Flex 1	Flex 2	Flex 3	Flex 4	Flex 5	Gyro X	Gyro Y	Gyro Z
أ	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-6,910.79	-14,692.16	-5,215.11
ب	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-15,701.58	-1,540.73	-7,971.96
ت	0.0	1.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	-16,344.69	700.44	-1,840.04
ث	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	-16,101.21	1,346.71	749.36
..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..

Fig 5: Flow of Axis, how the signs are converted to text, grammar check and when converted to speech using Arabic TTS.

The Arabic Text-to-Speech model was trained on Nawar Halabi's Arabic Speech Corpus. An MSA, single-speaker speech corpus for the purpose of speech synthesis was created alongside the tools required to create such a corpus. An MSA phonetics and phonology study was conducted to build those

tools, and finally, the corpus and these tools were evaluated (objectively and subjectively). [10]

We opted for Tacotron2 because it demonstrated superior performance and quality in our evaluations. The Tacotron2 research paper served as a notable inspiration, prompting us to incorporate their proposed solution into our own system. In Figure 6, it showcases the block diagram of the Tacotron 2 system architecture. Tacotron 2, is a neural network architecture for speech synthesis directly from text. The system is composed of a recurrent sequence-to-sequence feature prediction network that maps character embeddings to mel-scale spectrograms, followed by a modified WaveNet model acting as a vocoder to synthesize time-domain waveforms from those spectrograms. [11]

Fig 6: Tacotron 2 block image architecture.

V. CONCLUSION

While Axis shows promise, we recognize there's still plenty of room to grow, particularly in accurately distinguishing between certain sign language gestures. In Arabic Sign Language, where some signs for different letters bear a strong resemblance, getting it right every time can be challenging. However, what sets our approach apart is the innovative

integration of smart glove technology with grammar checking and Arabic Text-to-Speech capabilities.

The inclusion of a grammar check component adds a unique dimension to our solution. It provides users with an added layer of assurance that they're signing the correct letters accurately in Arabic Sign Language. Notably, our research revealed a scarcity of studies focusing on incorporating grammar checks into sign language systems, making our work a pioneering endeavor in this field.

Looking ahead, we see tremendous potential for the future applications of Axis. As technology continues to advance, we envision our smart glove technology making significant strides, not only in facilitating seamless communication but also in fostering a deeper integration of the Arabic language within the realm of technological innovations.

Despite these advancements, we remain humble and acknowledge that there's still much to learn and improve upon with Axis, while innovative, is just the beginning of what we hope will be a broader exploration into enhancing the accessibility and inclusivity of Arabic Sign Language communication. We believe that by remaining open to feedback and collaboration, we can further refine our approach and contribute meaningfully to the intersection of language, technology, and accessibility.

VI. REFERENCES

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